

SHORT NOTES

Applications of Refractive Index in the Study of Chemical Constitution

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Refractive index has long been considered to be intimately connected with chemical constitution. But in the expressions utilising this property for structural studies, another property, characteristic of the substance, mostly density, has also been used.

An attempt has been made to develop an expression, involving only the refractive index, which would be additive and constitutive. From amongst a large number of expressions studied, a function, 'characteristic of the molecule', $K_r = M/(n^2 + 2)$, has been found to be the most satisfactory. Incidentally, this expression is also obtained by dividing the Lorentz-Lorenz function,

$$\frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{d}$$

by that of the Newton-Laplace $(n^2 - 1) \times M/d$ and then multiplying this by the molecular weight M . It has an advantage in that only one determination is necessary. The theoretical interpretation is, however, not clear.

A single refractivity expression has not been found to interpret satisfactorily the effects of temperature and the chemical constitution'. The function K_r is not independent of temperature. But for a definite wave length and temperature, it is additive and constitutive. The wave length and temperature chosen by us are for the D-line and 20° respectively (i.e. n_D^{20}).

The refractive_D index values (n_D^{20}) for calculating K_r have been taken mostly from the work of Vogel *et al.*² The mean value of CH_2 increment (3.37) has been obtained by the usual method from nine homologous series: saturated hydrocarbons, alkyl chlorides, bromides and iodides, ethers, acetals, ketones, esters, aromatic hydrocarbons. Some other atomic, group, and structural values are recorded in Table I.

1. Kurtz and Ward, *J. Franklin Inst.*, 1936, 222,, 563; 1937, 224, 583, 697.

2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933 to 1948.

TABLE I

Atomic, group, and structural values of K_r .

O	1.45	NH ₂ (in primary aliphatic amines)	4.08
H(in CH ₂)	0.90	NH ₂ (in primary aromatic amines)	3.50
O (in ethers)	3.98	NH (in secondary aliphatic amines)	3.32
CO (in ketones)	6.52	NH (in secondary aromatic amines)	2.61
Cl (aliphatic)	8.82	N (in tertiary aliphatic amines)	2.30
Cl (aromatic)	8.90	N (in tertiary aromatic amines)	1.81
Br (aliphatic)	18.94	NO ₂ (aliphatic)	11.40
Br (aromatic)	18.29	NO ₂ (aromatic)	10.79
I (aliphatic)	28.86	ONO (nitrito)	12.00
I (aromatic)	26.98	N.NO (in nitrosoamine)	0.74
F (aliphatic)	5.64	NO (nitroso, aliphatic)	7.39
F (aromatic)	6.04	NO (nitroso, aromatic)	7.35
OH (in alcohols)	4.20	CN (aliphatic)	6.59
COO (in esters)	10.65	S ⁻ N (in thiocyanates)	13.34
COOH (in acids)	11.18	NCS (in isothiocyanates)	12.77
CH ₃	4.33	NO ₃ (aliphatic)	15.62
C ₆ H ₅ (phenyl)	17.13	S (in aliphatic sulphides)	6.00
C ₃ H ₇ (isopropyl)	11.22	S (in aromatic sulphides)	6.28
C ₄ H ₉ (isobutyl)	14.54	S ₂ (in aliphatic disulphides)	13.26
CO ₂ (aliphatic)	14.76	SH (in aliphatic thiols)	7.85
PO ₄ (aliphatic)	22.73	SH (in aromatic thiols)	7.20
Three-carbon ring	0.85	SO ₃ (aliphatic)	18.11
Four-carbon ring	0.83	SO ₄ (aliphatic)	23.44
Five-carbon ring	0.81	Carbon-carbon double bond	1.08
Six-carbon ring	0.82	Carbon-carbon triple bond	2.18

The new function K_r has been applied to some problems of chemical constitution and has been found to be no less satisfactory than other constants, besides has the advantage of involving only one experimental determination. A brief account of some of them is given below.

Optical Anomalies in Conjugated Systems.—Observed K_r values exhibit depression in case of conjugated compounds, comparable with exaltation observed in the case of their R_L values³.

Keto-enol Tautomerism.—The constant K_r has been employed for finding the %enol in compounds (e.g. ethyl butyryl⁴ malonate) comes out to 56.7 (55% from R_L value⁴). Similarly other tautomeric compounds, in which there is no resonance, give comparable values.

Application of Straight Line Mixture Law.—In two-component mixtures, when one is non-polar, it has generally been found that the K_r value determined from the solution agrees with its observed value. This value is often in close agreement when the solution is concentrated, but in some cases is slightly influenced by concentration. (Thus K_r values of 1,4-dioxane from solution in benzene are 21.75 for m.f. 0.0298 and 21.88 for m.f. 0.9050, against the observed value 21.89.)

³ J. Chem. Soc., Brühl, 1907, 92, 115; Auwers, Ber., 1928, 61B, 1041.

⁴ Auwers and Jacobson, Annalen, 1932, 426, 161.

The refractive index, n_D^{20} , of solids can be calculated from their solutions by first determining their K_r values. Thus n_D^{20} of *p*-dibromobenzene from solution in benzene is 1.5671 (calc. from K_r is 1.5679).

Structural Variations.—Isomeric groups and compounds, in which the mode of linking of multivalent atoms is different, show appreciable difference in their K_r values. Thus nitrite and nitro groups in aliphatic compounds show a difference of 0.60 in their K_r values (R_L diff. 0.52); difference in thiocyanate and isothiocyanate groups is 0.59 (R_L diff. 2.21). In case of branched chain and orientation isomers, difference in K_r values have also been observed.

K_r values for bonds have been worked out in case of a few organo-metallic compounds and the results appear as satisfactory as in the case of molar refraction.

Thus in view of the simplicity of determination of this new function, it may prove useful for problems of chemical constitution.

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